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2 Status and Change History

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3 Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to identify the main use cases for the gateway itself and for each scientific gateway on which the test specifications are created. These test specifications are the basis of acceptance test implementations.

For the collection of test specifications a template has been produced by WP5/SA2. The appendix of this document contains the template. It collects information on the background of testing - main functionalities (uses cases) and eventually the technical environment. It also contains the goal of testing, pre and post conditions, expected result, the most appropriate test type to be applied, special constraints of the test execution and the priority of tests. Additionally, information on the most appropriate working procedure with all the partners, contact persons and possible start date of testing also has been collected.

This document contains a condensed information of the collected test cases focusing on the test descriptions. The original specifications from all the JRA1 and JRA2 partners are stored in the official project repository in svn (see [https://cvs.lpd.sztaki.hu/scibus/wsvn/scibus/sa2/Test specifications/](https://cvs.lpd.sztaki.hu/scibus/wsvn/scibus/sa2/Test%20specifications/)). These specifications are live documents and will be updated as the project evolves.

Then this document contains sections on JRA1 tests specifications, respectively,

- JRA1 – gUSE implementation
- JRA1 - gUSE CloudBroker integration
- CloudBroker and ScaleTools Test Specifications

It then contains separate sections for each JRA2 portal:

- Statistical seismology science gateway (METU)
- Swiss systems biology community science gateway (ETH Zurich)
- German MoSGrid chemist community science gateway (EKUT)
- Amsterdam Medical Centre hospital gateway (AMC)
- PireGrid community commercial gateway (UNIZAR-BIFI)
- Commercial gateway for business process optimisation (SIMSOFT)
- Blender rendering community gateway (LU)
- Citizen web community gateway (EG)
- Astrophysics community science gateway (INAF)
- Build and test public gateway for application developers (4D)
- Helio-physics gateway (TCD)

JRA1 related test specifications are more detailed, as they provide the services which are the basis for JRA2 portals. JRA1 related test implementations are under development. The build and test environment is already operational in the 4D Etics Portal (etics3.4dsoft.hu) – the build and test environment for the SCI-BUS project. Builds and tests are implemented and running. More information on 4D Etics Portal can be found in the previous SA2 deliverable stored in svn

https://cvs.lpds.sztaki.hu/scibus/wsvn/scibus/sa2/Deliverables/DSA21/D51Integration_and_testing_strategy.doc in chapter 5.1.

On the other hand, the JRA2 portals test specifications are less detailed, mainly high level summaries are given, as they now implement the gUSE related new functionalities on which the tests focus on.

4 JRA1 – gUSE implementation

Portal, Work Package: gUSE implementation, JRA1

Organisation: MTA SZTAKI

Background for testing

For gUSE services the following test activities have been identified:

- testing of gUSE deployments by verifying WFI (Workflow Interpreter) service
- API tests
- End-to-end acceptance tests and performance tests

This section gives an overview on the self-tests of the WFI services, which are under development now (see etics3.4dsoft.hu gUSE project gUSE-test-cov configuration).

WFI is the workflow interpreter engine of the WS-Prgrade - gUse system. It reads a graph based workflow description and controls the order of generations and of submissions of the unique job instances belonging to a given workflow.

The WFI is sophisticated and complicated because of two circumstances:

1. The workflows which are designed and elaborated by the WS-Prgrade - gUse infrastructure may be rich of functionalities (parameter sweep feature including generator and collector jobs, embedded workflow call, input port value based conditional job execution, sophisticated error propagation).
2. The gUse (including the WFI) is built in a scalable, distributed way; each building block is implemented by a different service.

The praxis has proved that the reliable maintenance of the WFI (development and new installation as well) requires a well defined set of test workflows whose successful elaboration proves the correctness of the expected behaviour workflow interpreter.

In order that to distinguish eventual errors of the WFI from the errors of the back end part of the WS-Prgrade - gUse system, the test workflows mentioned above use a special, simulated resource, the “Local resource”.

The Local resource has three important advantages against a real “grid like” resource.

1. It is reliable. (Real grid resources are generally burdened with stochastic errors, because they compose huge distributed systems over several administration domains).
2. Its fast, as it is implemented “near” to the host of the WFI, on the same local network.
3. It needs no certificates that tend to expire, and therefore require special care.

The test workflows are designed such a way that they must fulfil the following additional requirements:

- No manual configuration is needed i.e. the workflow can be submitted automatically at any time.
- The workflow must behave deterministic. In order to ensure this condition it is assumed that the executables of jobs of the test workflows are tested under Scientific Linux / INTEL 64 chip set.
- The outcome of the result delivered by a test workflow can be evaluated in an automatic way. In order to ensure this condition each test workflow must contain a distinguished job named “FINAL-EVAL”.
- The functionality of a single test workflow must check the behaviour a selected part of the WFI functionality. The set of test workflows must cover all known features of the WFI.

A test workflow submission is regarded to be successful if two conditions are fulfilled together:

1. Just a single instance of the job FINAL-EVAL will be created in the final (or terminated) state of the workflow submission, and
2. The state of this job is “finished”.

In the current implementation of the test workflows the job FINAL-EVAL has two extended services may be used by a proper evaluation system:

If the job terminates then it creates two output files: “OUTPUT” is a text file and its content may be either “TRUE” or “FALSE” and “OUTPUT-VERBOSE” may contain a more detailed hint about the eventual error.

The test suite example below describes the scenario of running a couple of self testable workflows in the 4D ETICS Build Portal (gUSE-test-cov configuration under gUSE project).

Test Suites

Test Suite Name 1.: Self test of the WFI of the WS-Prgrade - gUse infrastructure

Goal	The purpose of this test is to validate the WFI service by running a couple of self testable workflows (see Background section).
Environment Prerequisites	gUSE project is added to Build Portal of the SCI-BUS. gUSE test configuration (test running environment) is created.
Pre-condition	The self-testable workflows have to be added in the initial database.
Test suite/case description, steps	Testing steps are comprised of calling different WFI services having as parameters the self-testable workflows.
Expected result	All the running workflows have to return 'True'.

5 JRA1 - gUSE CloudBroker integration

Portal Name: gUSE CloudBroker integration

Organisation, Workpackage: MTA SZTAKI, WP7/JRA1

Background for testing

MTA SZTAKI is implementing the low-level connection between WS-PGRADE/gUSE and the CloudBroker platform. The aim of the development is to enable WS-PGRADE users the exploitation of CloudBroker-provided SaaS services. The development from MTA SZTAKI's point of view consists of the following areas:

- develop a new DCI Bridge plugin for submitting jobs to the CloudBroker platform,
- develop a new portlet for specifying the user's CloudBroker credentials to interface with the CloudBroker platform,
- integrate necessary CloudBroker-related job configuration changes into the existing workflow configuration portlet of WS-PGRADE.

The task of the DCI Bridge plugin is to accept jobs from the WFI (workflow interpreter) component of gUSE, and run the jobs within the CloudBroker platform. The DCI Bridge accepts jobs described using a JSDL job description document through a standardized BES interface. It follows from this, that the DCI Bridge can be tested either from WS-PGRADE/gUSE or independently as a separate service. Testing from WS-PGRADE/gUSE can be achieved by using prepared workflows, whereas testing directly requires properly prepared JSDL documents.

The CloudBroker credential portlet is used to set the user's CloudBroker Platform username and password for any job submitted to the CloudBroker Platform from WS-PGRADE/gUSE. This can be performed through a very simple form where the user can set two values in the free-form text input fields.

Finally, the CloudBroker-related extension of the workflow configuration portlet are necessary to enable users the configuration of jobs submitted to the CloudBroker Platform. Within the portlet the user should be able to select CloudBroker as the submission target for the job. After this, the portlet should enable users to set all the necessary parameters for the job required by the CloudBroker Platform, for example the name of the application to run, the resource to use, etc.

Test Suites

Test Suite Name 1.: Test the CloudBroker Platform plugin of DCI Bridge directly.

Goal	The goal of this test suite is to test the functionality of the CloudBroker Platform plugin of DCI Bridge by calling the DCI Bridge service directly.
Environment Prerequisites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4D ETICS Build Portal • SCI-BUS CloudBroker Platform

Pre-condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployed DCI Bridge service with CloudBroker plugin (i.e., gUSE/WS-PGRADE built based on the gUSE-34-CloudBroker branch) • CloudBroker credentials ready for use • At least one application deployed in CloudBroker
Test suite/case description	<p>A set of predefined JSDLs should be submitted to the DCI Bridge service. The JSDL should reflect the following settings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JSDL configured for proper CloudBroker Platform execution, • misconfigured JSDL (e.g. not existing application, mistyped resource, etc.)
Expected result	<p>The expected result for properly configured JSDLs is that the jobs terminate successfully and output files are available. The expected result for misconfigured JSDLs is that the DCI Bridge should report the job as failed containing the error reported by CloudBroker Platform.</p>
Constraints for test execution	<p>A CloudBroker Platform credential is needed for performing the tests.</p>

Test Suite Name 2.: Test the CloudBroker Platform plugin of DCI Bridge through prepared workflows (WFI test).

Goal	<p>The goal of this test suite is to test the functionality of the CloudBroker Platform plugin of DCI Bridge through using the whole WS-PGRADE/gUSE system.</p>
Environment Prerequisites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4D ETICS Build Portal • SCI-BUS CloudBroker Platform
Pre-condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete deployed WS-PGRADE/gUSE service stack with enabled CloudBroker DCI Bridge plugin (gUSE/WS-PGRADE built based on the gUSE-34-CloudBroker branch) • CloudBroker credentials ready for use • At least one application deployed in CloudBroker • The self-testable workflows have to be added in the initial database.
Test suite/case description	<p>Testing steps are comprised of calling different WFI services having as parameters the self-testable workflows.</p>
Expected result	<p>All the running workflows have to return 'True'.</p>

Test Suite Name 3.: Test the CloudBroker credential portlet.

Goal	<p>The goal of this test suite is to test the functionality of the CloudBroker credential portlet.</p>
Environment Prerequisites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4D ETICS Build Portal
Pre-condition	<p>Deployed WS-PGRADE service (gUSE/WS-PGRADE built based on the gUSE-34-CloudBroker branch)</p>
Test suite/case description	<p>Testing steps are comprised of simulating usage of the CloudBroker credential portlet. The following test cases are available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "user" sets some valid credentials (e.g. an e-mail address and some password) • "user" set some random data for the CloudBroker username and password
Expected result	<p>Basically, the portlet should accept and save the credentials in every case.</p>

Test Suite Name 4.: Test the workflow configuration portlet with CloudBroker extension.

Goal	<p>The goal of this test suite is to test the functionality of the concrete workflow portlet's workflow configuration part extended with configuring CloudBroker jobs.</p>
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4D ETICS Build Portal

Prerequisites	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• SCI-BUS CloudBroker platform
Pre-condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Complete deployed WS-PGRADE/gUSE service stack with enabled CloudBroker DCI Bridge plugin (gUSE/WS-PGRADE built based on the gUSE-34-CloudBroker branch)• CloudBroker credentials ready for use• At least one application deployed in CloudBroker
Test suite/case description	Testing steps are comprised of simulating usage of the Concrete workflow portlet's workflow configuration part. The simulated user should click a node of a workflow to configure, select the job to run using the CloudBroker Platform, select all the properties for the job, and save the workflow.
Expected result	The configuration of the workflow should be successful in every case.

6 CloudBroker and ScaleTools Test Specifications

Portal Name: Commercial Components in Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE

Organisation, Workpackage: CB and ST, JRA1 / WP7

Background for testing

Within SCI-BUS, the connection to commercial clouds and the integration of billing facilities is performed by means of the CloudBroker Platform, using its REST and Java APIs. Together, this is called the “commercial components”. For the commercial components, the following functionalities are implemented into Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE as part of work package JRA1 / WP7:

1. Integration of the CloudBroker Platform into the DCI Bridge, security credentials and job configuration and management (mainly responsible: MTA SZTAKI)
2. Enabling of cost estimates and display as well as billing functionalities based on different mappings of users between Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE and the CloudBroker Platform and different cost display filters (mainly responsible: CB and ST)
3. Implementation of interfaces to open source-based cloud infrastructure tools such as Eucalyptus, OpenStack and OpenNebula in the CloudBroker Platform (mainly responsible: CB and ST)
4. Porting of applications necessary for the various SCI-BUS gateways to the interfaced cloud infrastructures (mainly responsible: CB and ST)
5. Further optional functionalities depending on project requirements, such as automatic deployments and running full workflows as a service

The goal of this chapter is to describe the necessary integration testing between Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE and the CloudBroker Platform in more detail. It should be noted, though, that before being provided to this kind of testing any of the necessary changes done directly in the CloudBroker Platform runs through internal testing at CB and ST first. This in particular applies to:

- REST and Java API modifications and additions
- The new adapters to open cloud infrastructures
- Any additional applications or functionalities enabled in the CloudBroker Platform

Regarding the integration testing of the new implementations defined in points 1 to 5 above, one can separate between four groups of tests:

- A. Testing of the CloudBroker DCI Bridge, security credentials and job configuration and management (“gUSE CloudBroker integration”) – this covers point 1 above (mainly responsible: MTA SZTAKI, see chapter 5)

- B. Extension of test group A by user mapping, cost display and open cloud adapters – this covers a part of point 2 as well as point 3 above (mainly responsible: CB and ST in coordination with MTA SZTAKI)
- C. Testing of the different user mapping configurations and the cost and billing facilities beyond individual jobs and workflows – this covers the rest of point 2 above (mainly responsible: CB and ST)
- D. Testing of any extra applications and functionalities required by certain gateways or for special scenarios – this covers points 4 and 5 above (mainly responsible: JRA2 portal providers)

While test groups A and D are detailed in separate chapters, in the following test suites will be defined for test groups B and C, for which CB and ST take the main responsibility.

Test Suites

Test Suite Group B: Extension of gUSE CloudBroker integration testing (“test group A”) by user mapping, cost display and open cloud adapters

Goal	The goal of this test suite is to test the CloudBroker DCI Bridge, security credentials and job configuration and management in Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE regarding different settings for user mapping, cost display and open cloud adapters. For this, corresponding variants of the gUSE CloudBroker integration testing described in a separate chapter are performed.
Environment Prerequisites	The following environments have to be present: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4D ETICS Build Portal • SCI-BUS Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE installation • SCI-BUS CloudBroker Platform • Commercial and open cloud infrastructures
Pre-condition	The following prerequisites have to be fulfilled: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test group A successfully set up and performed • Necessary organizations and users enabled in Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE and in the CloudBroker Platform • Test software and resources (incl. open cloud adapters) available, configured and deployed in the CloudBroker Platform, also with corresponding prices
Test suite/case description	Selected tests of test group A are repeated in several variants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different types of user mapping (“one for all”, “whitelabeled”, “individual”) and cost display filtering • Different prices for software and resources • Selection of commercial or open cloud adapters
Expected result	The desired results of the tests are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results of test group A are still valid. • All test group B variants also finish successfully. • If necessary, suitable users are created in the CloudBroker Platform on demand. • Jobs are executed and accounted for correctly in the CloudBroker Platform (regarding user, resource, software, costs, etc.). • Cost estimates and displays in Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE are correctly filtered and correspond to those in the CloudBroker Platform.

Test Suite Group C: Testing of the different user mapping configurations and the cost and billing facilities beyond individual jobs and workflows

Goal	The goal of this test suite is to test the user mapping, cost display and billing functionalities within the SCI-BUS Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE and CloudBroker Platform integration that go beyond the execution of individual jobs and workflows. In
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	particular, the monthly billing facilities and display will be checked.
Environment Prerequisites	The following environments have to be present: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4D ETICS Build Portal • SCI-BUS Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE installation • SCI-BUS CloudBroker Platform • Commercial and open cloud infrastructures
Pre-condition	The following prerequisites have to be fulfilled: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test groups A and B successfully set up and performed • Possibility to create end of month invoices in the CloudBroker Platform upon UI and API request
Test suite/case description	These steps have to be executed: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Several tests of test group B are performed in different variants. 2. End of month invoices are created in the CloudBroker Platform.
Expected result	The desired results of the tests are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results of test group B are still valid. • All test group C variants also finish successfully. • Costs are accounted for correctly in the CloudBroker Platform (regarding price, user, organization, invoice, etc.). • Billing item and invoice displays in Liferay / WS-PGRADE / gUSE are correctly filtered and correspond to those in the CloudBroker Platform.

7 JRA2.1: Statistical seismology science gateway (METU)

Portal Name: Statistical Seismology Science Gateway

Organisation, Workpackage: METU, JRA2.1 – Statistical Seismology Science Gateway

Background for testing

The goal of the Statistical Seismology Science Gateway (SSS Gateway) is to provide robust and effective statistical methods in order to obtain more precise estimates, reduce uncertainties and conduct more reliable seismic hazard analysis. Hence, this science gateway aims to implement the following foremost statistical seismology functions (SSFs), reflecting the latest advances in the literature, for the international seismology community:

SSF1: Integration of multi-source data for increased reliability and quality

SSF2: Determination of probability distributions and their input parameters

SSF3: Robust techniques for the parameter estimation in models and relations

SSF4: Complex predictive modeling of earthquake phenomena in time-space domains

SSF5: Ground motion prediction equations

SSF6: Complex logic-tree and sensitivity analysis in probabilistic seismic hazard assessment

SSF7: Statistical calculations for seismic risk

These statistical seismology functions are aimed to be provided on a web-based science gateway for ease of access and use, offering a choice of three service levels for its users:

- Simple → A user can run and get the result of any of the SSFs for her/his data and parameters easily through the portlet with a GUI provided.
- Advanced → A user can code her/his models in a programming language (such as FORTRAN, MATLAB, Octave) calling any combination of the SSFs.
- Expert → A user can design and use her/his own improved workflow embedding the SSFs.

There will be

- Seven web test suites, one per SSF to test its simple use through a portlet provided;
- Seven API test suites, one per SSF to test its API;
- One web test suite to test the advanced use of SSFs;
- One deployment test suite to test the behaviour of the SSS gateway in a production environment.

No test suite has been specified for the expert use as it will be completely based on the WS-PGRADE/gUSE environment.

Test Suites

Goal	Testing the portlet for SSF1 – Integration of multi-source data for increased reliability and quality
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this portlet and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF1, through this portlet, in order to integrate some earthquake catalogs. User uploads her/his own catalog file(s) and/or selects catalogs from the provided repositories. User selects the options through the GUI of this portlet. User submits the workflow. User may check the execution status. User gets the resulting bundle when the workflow completes.
Expected result	A file containing the catalog integrated.

Goal	Testing the portlet for SSF2 – Determination of probability distributions and their input parameters
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this portlet and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF2, through this portlet, in order to determine the probability distribution of some earthquake catalog and its parameters. User uploads her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User selects the options through the GUI of this portlet. User submits the workflow. User may check the execution status. User gets the resulting bundle when the workflow completes.
Expected result	A file, per magnitude PDF selected/suggested, containing the parameters of that PDF.

Goal	Testing the portlet for SSF3 – Robust techniques for the parameter estimation in models and relations
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this portlet and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF3, through this portlet, in order to determine the parameters of seismicity models or relations for some earthquake catalog. User uploads her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User selects the options through the GUI of this portlet. User submits the workflow. User may check the execution status. User gets the resulting bundle when the workflow completes.
Expected result	A file, per seismicity model or relation selected, containing the parameters of that model or relation.

Goal	Testing the portlet for SSF4 – Complex predictive modeling of earthquake phenomena in time-space domains
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this portlet and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF4, through this portlet, in order to determine the parameters of seismic hazard assessment models for some earthquake catalog. User uploads her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User selects the options through the GUI of this portlet. User submits the workflow. User may check the execution status. User gets the resulting bundle when the workflow completes.
Expected result	A file, per seismic hazard assessment model selected, containing the parameters of that model.

Goal	Testing the portlet for SSF5 – Ground motion prediction equations
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this portlet and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF5, through this portlet, in order to determine the parameters of ground motion prediction equations (GMPE) for some earthquake catalog and to calculate the intensity measures. User uploads her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User provides a separate file for each GMPE selected containing its inputs. User selects the options through the GUI of this portlet. User submits the workflow. User may check the execution status. User gets the resulting bundle when the workflow completes.
Expected result	One file, per GMPEs selected, containing the parameters of that GMPE and its calculated intensity measures.

Goal	Testing the portlet for SSF6 – Complex logic-tree and sensitivity analysis in probabilistic seismic hazard assessment
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this portlet and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF6, through this portlet, in order to have seismic hazard calculation results of a logic-tree for some earthquake catalog. User uploads her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User provides a file describing the nodes of a logic-tree. User selects the options through the GUI of this portlet. User submits the workflow. User may check the execution status. User gets the resulting bundle when the workflow completes.
Expected result	A file, per each node of the logic-tree, containing its seismic hazard calculation results.

Goal	Testing the portlet for SSF7 – Statistical calculations for seismic risk
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this portlet and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF7, through this portlet, in order to have seismic risk calculation results based on seismic risk models for some earthquake catalog. User uploads her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User selects the options through the GUI of this portlet. User submits the workflow. User may check the execution status. User gets the resulting bundle when the workflow completes.

Goal	Testing the API for SSF1 – Integration of multi-source data for increased reliability and quality
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this API and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF1, through this API, in order to integrate some earthquake catalogs. User provides the zip INP1 holding her/his own catalog file(s) and/or references to catalogs selected from the provided repositories. User provides the file INP2 containing the options. User calls SSF1(INP1, INP2, OUT). User gets the resulting file OUT.
Expected result	The file OUT containing the catalog integrated.

Goal	Testing the API for SSF2 – Determination of probability distributions and their input parameters
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this API and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF2, through this API, in order to determine the probability distribution of some earthquake catalog and its parameters. User provides the file INP1 containing her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User provides the file INP2 containing the options. User calls SSF2(INP1, INP2, OUT). User gets the resulting zip OUT.
Expected result	The zip OUT holding a separate file, per magnitude PDF selected/suggested, containing the parameters of that PDF.

Goal	Testing the API for SSF3 – Robust techniques for the parameter estimation in models and relations
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this API and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF3, through this API, in order to determine the parameters of seismicity models or relations for some earthquake catalog. User provides the file INP1 containing her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User provides the file INP2 containing the options. User calls SSF3(INP1, INP2, OUT). User gets the resulting zip OUT.
Expected result	The zip OUT holding a separate file, per seismicity model or relation selected, containing the parameters of that model or relation.

Goal	Testing the API for SSF4 – Complex predictive modeling of earthquake phenomena in time-space domains
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this API and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF4, through this API, in order to determine the parameters of seismic hazard assessment models for some earthquake catalog. User provides the file INP1 containing her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User provides the file INP2 containing the options. User calls SSF6(INP1, INP2, OUT). User gets the resulting zip OUT.
Expected result	The zip OUT holding a separate file, per seismic hazard assessment model selected, containing the parameters of that model.

Goal	Testing the API for SSF5 – Ground motion prediction equations
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this API and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF5, through this API, in order to determine the parameters of ground motion prediction equations (GMPE) for some earthquake catalog and to calculate the intensity measures. User provides the file INP1 containing her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User provides the file INP2 containing the options. User provides the zip INP3 holding a separate file for each GMPE selected containing its inputs. User calls SSF4(INP1, INP2, INP3, OUT). User gets the resulting zip OUT.
Expected result	The zip OUT holding a separate file, per GMPEs selected, containing the parameters of that GMPE and its calculated intensity measures.

Goal	Testing the API for SSF6 – Complex logic-tree and sensitivity analysis in probabilistic seismic hazard assessment
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this API and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF6, through this API, in order to have seismic hazard calculation results of a logic-tree for some earthquake catalog. User provides the file INP1 containing her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User provides the file INP2 containing the options. User calls SSF5(INP1, INP2, OUT). User gets the resulting zip OUT.
Expected result	The zip OUT holding a separate file, per each node of the logic-tree, containing its seismic hazard calculation results.

Goal	Testing the API for SSF7 – Statistical calculations for seismic risk
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this API and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use SSF7, through this API, in order to have seismic risk calculation results based on seismic risk models for some earthquake catalog. User provides the file INP1 containing her/his own catalog file or selects a catalog from the provided repositories. User provides the file INP2 containing the options. User calls SSF7(INP1, INP2, OUT). User gets the resulting zip OUT.
Expected result	The zip OUT holding a separate file, per each seismic risk model selected, containing its seismic risk calculation results.

Goal	Testing the portlet for advanced use – A user can code her/his models in a programming language (such as FORTRAN, MATLAB, Octave) calling any combination of the SSFs
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this portlet and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use execute, through this portlet, her/his own model written in a programming language calling any combination of the SSFs. User provides the source code of her/his model together with all the input files needed by the SSF calls in the model. User compiles it. User executes the model. User gets the resulting zip.
Expected result	The zip holding one file/zip, per each SSF call made, containing the result of that SSF call.

Goal	Testing the Statistical Seismology Science Gateway in a production environment
Pre-condition	User has valid credentials to access this portlet and submit jobs to DCI.
Test suite/case description	User wants to use all the functionality provided by the portlets of this gateway as specified by the related test suites above.
Expected result	The portlets of the gateway function as specified by the related test suites above.

8 JRA2.2: Swiss systems biology community science gateway (ETH Zurich)

Portal Name: Swiss systems biology community science gateway

Organisation, Workpackage: ETHZ, JRA2.2

Background for testing

For providing the functionalities of the proteomics portal the following test cases need to be run on the portal source:

- Building the code of the proteomics web application
- Testing and verifying the general workflow parameterization framework (from reading the workflow specification from files to generating the necessary inputs for ASM based workflow submission)
- Validating the existing workflows descriptions (if they can be parsed without error by the framework)

To ease the development of the workflow specific portlets and to speed up the integration of new workflows, we developed a general framework which abstracts out the generalities of the proteomics workflow submission: input selection (connection with the openBIS data-manager), parameter settings (handling different argument types, value checks on this arguments, template specifications, allowing customization per user).

The integration of a workflow requires the specification of the following properties files:

- Workflow description: it contains the name of the workflow (display name, full name as the workflow available in the gUSE repository), on which job and which port(s) the input is expected, what kind of openBIS data selector is required, reference to the parameter descriptor file (see next item).
- Parameter definitions: this file describes all the input needed to be specified to run the workflow. Each input item has a key, type (like INTEGER, FLOAT, STRING, ENUM,..), default value, visibility setting, label and description to be displayed on the gui.
- Default values sets: these files provide use-case specific value settings for the parameters. Users can also save their favourite parameter settings to be able to start quicker next time an analysis.

More information on this approach will be given later on and will be added to the test specifications ([https://cvs.lpds.szaki.hu/scibus/wsvn/scibus/sa2/Test specifications/](https://cvs.lpds.szaki.hu/scibus/wsvn/scibus/sa2/Test%20specifications/)).

Test Suite Template(s)

1, Reading workflow definition from properties file

Goal	To verify the proteomics portal main functionalities like reading the necessary
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	information from the properties files, saving the modified values into default files per user, preparing the workflow input files.
Pre-condition	The test properties files should be provided with the expected workflow input files (should be generated from the property description) and should cover the majority of the possible customization options.
Test suite/case description	Read the provided test properties files contain valid workflow description and test if the built up java objects contains the appropriate values and are able to produce the parameter file expected by the workflows.
Expected result	The java objects have to be consistent with the properties and the workflow inputs produced by the portal code have to be equivalent with provided files.

2. Loading and saving the modified values of the workflow parameters from/into the user's default store directory

Goal	To verify the proteomics portal main functionalities like reading the necessary information from the properties files, saving the modified values into default files per user, preparing the workflow input files.
Pre-condition	The test properties files should be provided.
Test suite/case description	After reading a workflow description and performing some modification on the stored values (simulating the changes triggered by webgui interaction) the modified values have to be saved into the test user's defaults directory and then after reloading the original workflow description have to be loadable from the default file. The performed default value loading has to set the values according the test modification.
Expected result	The saved default values stores the values defined by the test modification and the loading of this file is able to set the values.

3. Validating the real workflow definition files used make the production workflows available

Goal	To verify the proteomics portal main functionalities like reading the necessary information from the properties files, saving the modified values into default files per user, preparing the workflow input files.
Pre-condition	The real workflow definition files should be provided with expected workflow inputs.
Test suite/case description	Loading the production workflow description files and generating the workflow input files.
Expected result	The generated workflow inputs have to be equivalent with the provided expected inputs.

4. Validating the generated web gui

Goal	To verify that the portal is able to generate the appropriate web gui from the workflow definition files.
Pre-condition	Providing a workflow definition which enables testing all the different input types.
Test suite/case description	Loading the workflow description file and checking the generated web page.
Expected result	The generated web page has to contain the controls according the workflow definition file (like if one of the properties is defined as a select-on-menu the web page have to contain a select menu).

9 JRA2.3: German MoSGrid chemist community science gateway (EKUT)

Portal Name: EKUT

Organisation, Workpackage: JRA2.3, WP8

Background for testing

Within the SCI-BUS project a semantic metadata search engine and WebGL based visualization of molecular data shall be implemented for the MoSGrid community. These two areas need to be tested. For the visualization performance, stability and compatibility are very important. For the metadata related topics consistency and error free conversions are essential.

1. WebGL based visualisation

Goal	Reliable molecular structure visualisation.
Environment	Various Windows, Linux and MAC environments in combination with multiple browsers (Internet Explorer, Firefox, Chrome, Safari).
Prerequisites	
Pre-condition	Access to MoSGrid portal?. A couple of different molecular structures (pdb, sdf format).
Test suite/case description	Load, visualize and manipulate molecular structures including access to a remote repository.
Expected result	Similar appearance and portlet behaviour on all typical platforms. Reference portlet appearance should be given.

2. Metadata Annotation / Semantic search

Goal	Ensure the consistency of metadata among all steps along the value chain.
Pre-condition	Ability to compare xml documents. MSML, a dialect of CML, is used throughout the portal/portlet related steps. After the workflow completion the metadata information is converted to JSON and stored within an XtreamFS repository.
Test suite/case description	
Expected result	Working loss-free adapter and parser steps.

10 JRA2.4: Amsterdam Medical Centre hospital gateway (AMC)

Portal Name: e-BioInfra Gateway

Organisation, Workpackage: AMC, WP8/JRA2

Background for testing

Application server: AMC uses Glassfish 3.1.1 for running web applications such as the current e-BioInfra Gateway (non-gUSE/Liferay), while currently we are also using Tomcat 6.0.32 for running the gUSE portal that will form the basis for the new e-BioInfra Gateway release. The use of Tomcat is temporary and the current plan is to migrate the gUSE/Liferay-based portal under Glassfish. Until this is accomplished, we would like to run some of the tests on Tomcat, some others on Glassfish, while we may require other tests to be executed on both application servers. We will specify this requirement under each test.

Browser support: we plan to provide support for Mozilla Firefox, Safari, and Internet Explorer, and we would like to test that the gateway functions correctly in all three browsers.

Liferay-specific testing: AMC is running Liferay 6.0.5 to comply with current gUSE version requirements. Liferay-specific test cases – such as login and new account creation functions – will not be defined in this document, except where it is critical to test specific conditions anticipated by portal configurations. For example, test cases will be defined to assess if the configuration of roles and permissions was done correctly.

Liferay user groupings: AMC will launch its application-specific gateway using the Brain Imaging Community as the pilot user group, and then proceed to accommodate the requirements of Sequencing and Virology users. We will most likely use the Liferay concept of Communities to group our users and assign permissions to them, according to these three user groups. This is mainly done for enabling sharing of workflows between the users of a particular group, while prohibiting non-community members from accessing these workflows. Tests have to be defined for assessing that permissions are correctly enforced. Besides Liferay Communities, we will define Liferay Organizations for grouping our users on a different level. Organizations will be necessary for handling other requirements, such as publishing announcements or sending emails to users of a particular group. Tests will also have to be defined for checking that only the intended users receive these emails or announcements.

Accounting data: We are currently using a robot certificate for enabling some of our users to run workflows through the gateway. There is a possibility that we switch some users to using their individual certificates in later versions, but for now we need to make sure that resource usage data is correctly collected through the Liferay gateway (attributed to the correct Liferay userID and VO), whether the user is running with their personal proxy or with the robot proxy. Additionally, if a user belongs to more than one supported VOs, we also need to make sure that the correct VO (as specified by the workflow developer) is used for executing a workflow, whether the user is running with their personal proxy or with the robot proxy.

Integration testing: Individual test cases for JRA1 portlets and middle-tier services provided by gUSE will not be defined, but it is necessary to execute those tests also. Any available DCI Bridge tests that are specific to gLite middleware are also necessary. Some functionality may not be used in the AMC-specific gateway, so not all JRA1 tests are applicable. All relevant JRA1 test cases will be referenced in this document.

Overview of all tests by category

Roles / permissions enforcement:

- community-owned workflows must be viewable only between members of the community

New functionality

- Provenance information portlet
- Grid monitoring

- neuroimaging workflows

Test AMC.01

Goal	It must be possible to exchange workflows between community members. Additionally, workflows must not be viewed without the correct permissions: workflow that is registered under a particular community (e.g. the Brain Imaging Community) must only be available to members of that community.
Pre-condition	User community <i>BIC</i> exists and has at least 3 members, <i>bicuser1</i> , <i>bicuser2</i> , and <i>bicwfdev1</i> . Different test input files available on LFC. At least two other non-administrative users <i>seuser1</i> and <i>seqwfdev1</i> exist in the system, and these users are not members of the community. At least one workflow <i>wfA</i> has been defined under <i>BIC</i> , created by user <i>bicwfdev1</i> . Proxy (test?) certificates are available for all users and associated with a gLite VO that will be used for testing (?).
Test suite/case description	(a) <i>bicuser1</i> logins, accesses Workflow > Concrete portlet, configures <i>wfA</i> inputs and submits the workflow... (b) ..
Expected result	Workflow <i>wfA</i> can be submitted by <i>bicuser1</i> , <i>bicuser2</i> , and <i>bicwfdev1</i> , and these users can access all <i>wfA</i> -related information (status) and results (std.out, std.err etc), as well as workflow provenance information. No information or results of <i>wfA</i> is accessible by <i>seuser1</i> or <i>seqwfdev1</i> .

Relevant JRA1 test cases

These test cases will be specified later on.

11 JRA2.5: PireGrid community commercial gateway (UNIZAR-BIFI)

Portal: DS1

Organisation: UniZar/BIFI, JRA2.5/WP8

Background for testing

These tests are meant to try the new specific portal functionalities, to find possible bugs, and to guarantee its proper working. The main aspects that we want to test are:

- Connections to DCI bridge for dynamically manage the available resources
- Dynamic creation and configuration of servers in order to run MapReduce jobs
- Test the new portlets developed for MapReduce job executing
- Proper executions of MapReduce jobs in this servers

For testing DCIs connections, all the necessary information will be given, and every URL has to be tested for proper answer.

The dynamic build servers will be created in the PireGRID infrastructure. Their lifecycle will be managed dynamically, and the proper creation of these servers has to be tested and guaranteed. All this servers will be created dynamically once they are needed meanwhile there are enough free resources in the infrastructure.

There will be three new portlets that have to be tested. The import portlet, which is the application that will help the user to upload his jobs, the run job portlet, that will be capable of configure the resources used by the job and run it displaying its progress, and the history portlet, in which the user will be available to see a history of all of his jobs with their results.

After all of it has been tested, it has to be tested all-together, and the best way to do it is running a MapReduce job using the gateway. The job run has to be tested before in an independent MapReduce infrastructure. After running the job in both of the infrastructures successfully, the results have to be compared in order to assure the proper working of the gateway.

All these new functionalities will be tested mostly at service and API level. However, a few business level end-to-end acceptance tests are also foreseen.

The main purpose of the following scenario is to verify the required functionalities of the Build Portal from end user point of view. To do so, business level acceptance tests to verify remote MapReduce job.

Test Suites

Test Suite Name1: Business scenario for remote MapReduce job submission on cloud through DCI Bridge

Goal	To have end-to-end acceptance tests to validate the whole business logic in case of remote MapReduce job submission on cloud environment
Environment Prerequisites	The portal can be tested from any system with any SO, it is just needed a regular browser and the MapReduce job files.
Pre-condition	The user of the Build Portal is already registered and he has to belong to the community of MapReduce. The project configuration under test is already created.
Test suite/case description, steps	<p>Feature: MapReduce job execution</p> <p>User Story: Run a MapReduce job on cloud transparently through the Build Portal</p> <p>Scenario happy path</p> <p>Given a registered user with login name "Smiths" that belongs to the MapReduce community of the gateway And release manager rights. When user is logging in as "Smiths" having access to gUSE project, Then user "Smiths" acces the gateway MapReduce section, And user "Smiths" submit the remote job configuring the parameters as he wants And user "Smiths" follows the status of the submission. When the status is finished Then user "Smiths" can download the results</p> <p>Scenario insufficient privileges</p> <p>Given a registered user with login name "Smiths", And not belonging to the MapReduce comunity. When user is logging in as "Smiths" having access to gUSE project, Then user "Smiths" acces the gateway MapReduce section, And user "Smiths" receives a missing rights message.</p>
Expected result	The user views in his screen a link for downloading the results of the run job.

12 JRA2.6: Commercial gateway for business process optimisation (SIMSOFT)

Portal Name: Business Process Optimisation

Organisation, Workpackage: Simsoft, JRA2.6

Background for testing

Test specification for Simsoft gateway covers the main functionalities of gateway. These are user, general and simulation functionalities of gateway.

Main task of Simsoft Gateway is to simulate multiple Business Processes at Grid Environment. Business Processes are designed by using Bonita Solution Software and the export files of these processes (.bar files) are used as input file for Gateway.

Considering the test of Simsoft Gateway Test Environment is formed by WS-PGRADE Portal, Simsoft Gateway and SZTAKI Desktop Grid Environment. During Testing the person who tests the gateway is referred as "User".

This document will be updated during project as the new functionalities are added and the present ones are changed.

At this stage of project test cases of gateway presents rough overview of software compared to final implementation of software. As the implementation of gateway advances, test cases will be more detailed.

Test Suite: General Functionality of Gateway

Test Case: Displaying Error Message

Goal	To display error message
Pre-condition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An empty rar file is created with named "SomeFile.rar" SomeFile.rar must be available for testing.
Test suite/case description, steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The User uploads the input file which is called as SomeFile.rar The User receives the error message of "Upload Error: Input file named 'SomeFile.rar' is not a proper Business Process file "
Expected result	The gateway shows the message of "Upload Error: Input file named 'SomeFile.rar' is not a proper Business Process file "

Test Suite: Simulation Scenario for Business Process

Test Case: Uploading of Input files (Business Processes)

Goal	To upload the input files of the business processes
Pre-condition	The BusinessProcessName1.bar and BusinessProcessName2.bar must have been designed by BONITA software and must have been exported as a .bar file.
Test suite/case description, steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The User uploads the input files which are BusinessProcessName1.bar and BusinessProcessName2.bar The User validates the input files The User receives the message of "Validation of Input Files is successful"
Expected result	The gateway shows the message of "Validation of Input Files is successful"
Constraints for test	Input files must be named by following pattern:

execution	<p>[BusinessProcessName][FileNumber].bar</p> <p>Example of input file names: BusinessProcessName1.bar BusinessProcessName2.bar .. BusinessProcessNameN.bar</p> <p>The names of business process files (BusinessProcessName) must be the same, but the file numbers (FileNumber) must increment consecutively.</p>
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Test Case: Simulation of Business Processes

Goal	To run simulation of business processes at the Grid Environment
Pre-condition	Test Case: Uploading of Input files (Business Processes) must be done successfully.
Test suite/case description/steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user selects the Grid Environment • The user sends the input files for simulation to Grid Environment • The user receives the message of “Simulation has started successfully” • The user follows status information of simulation • When the status is finished; • The user receives the message of “Simulation has finished successfully”
Expected result	The gateway shows the messages of Simulation has started and finished successfully

Test Case: Viewing the Results of Simulation

Goal	To view the results of Simulation
Pre-condition	Test Case: Simulation of Business Processes must be done successfully.
Test suite/case description/steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When the status of simulation is finished • The User downloads the results of simulation
Expected result	Result file of simulation must be available for download.

13 JRA2.7: Blender rendering community gateway (LU)

Portal Name: Blender rendering community gateway

Organisation, Workpackage: LU, JRA2.7

Background for testing

The test plan for LU covers the tests that are required to ensure that the contact points between LU and the partners works. The bulk of the processes will be handled through the workflow pattern, with an adapted uploader at the core of the workflow.

The areas to be tested can roughly be divided in areas for authentication, session and result creation, result delivery, status checking and error handling.

Test specifications will be kept up-to-date during the project. Pay specific attention to naming of status and error messages, as they can change during the project phase. Also changes in workflow and dataflow will be reflected here where needed.

At this point of the project the test cases represent a rough overview of the issues that need to be tested to ensure both proper working of the Renderfarm.fi backend and the integration with and to partner portals and grids. Due to the nature of the test cases most of them will also look like use cases.

Test Suit: inbound work

These test cases are for inbound work. This means sessions sent to the Renderfarm.fi backend by SCI-BUS project partners.

Goal	Authentication of partner
Pre-condition	Not authenticated.
Test suite/case description/steps	Verify the partner connection attempt. Accept certificate when presented and validated.
Expected result	The partner is authenticated.

Goal	Create new user
Pre-condition	No user account exists for partner
Test suite/case description/steps	Create a new user account in the backend
Expected result	New user account exists

Goal	Log existing user in
Pre-condition	User account exists.
Test suite/case description/steps	Authenticate and log user account in.
Expected result	User account is logged in.

Goal	Receive job
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Pre-condition	User has .blend file ready for upload. The .blend-file can be called a session
Test suite/case description/steps	The user uploads the file using workflow.
Expected result	The session has been uploaded to the backend and put into review queue

Goal	Create resulting files
Pre-condition	User has successfully uploaded a session
Test suite/case description/steps	The session is being rendered on Renderfarm.fi.
Expected result	The rendered result is available for download.

Goal	Render on Renderfarm.fi::deliver results
Pre-condition	The rendered result is available for download.
Test suite/case description/steps	Notify the user of the result files.
Expected result	The user has received a list of links to the result files and can access them.

Goal	Render on Renderfarm.fi::work cancellation
Pre-condition	A session has been uploaded.
Test suite/case description/steps	Cancel further processing of the session.
Expected result	The session is no longer being processed.

Goal	Render on Renderfarm.fi::user cancels workflow
Pre-condition	A workflow is active
Test suite/case description/steps	The user is able to cancel the workflow
Expected result	The workflow and corresponding session or sessions have been cancelled

Goal	Render on Renderfarm.fi::review queue
Pre-condition	A session is in the review queue
Test suite/case description/steps	The user is able to cancel the session in this stage
Expected result	The session has been removed from the review queue and is no longer being processed on Renderfarm.fi. Session is removed from review queue and won't be handled any further.

Goal	Render on Renderfarm.fi::render queue
Pre-condition	A session is in the render queue
Test suite/case description/steps	Cancel the ongoing rendering of the rendering process
Expected result	The session is removed from the render queue. Render clients have been notified.

Goal	Error handling::upload fails
Pre-condition	User is uploading a session.
Test suite/case description/steps	The upload fails.
Expected result	The user is notified through the workflow of the aborted upload process.

Goal	Error handling::to many submitted sessions
Pre-condition	User has reached maximum amount of open sessions.

Test suite/case description/steps	User starts upload of new session.
Expected result	User is notified that there are too many open sessions for the account.

Goal	Error handling::session aborted
Pre-condition	Session is in the review or render queue of Renderfarm.fi
Test suite/case description/steps	Renderfarm.fi administrator cancels (review queue) or aborts (render queue) the session.
Expected result	User is notified that the session is cancelled or aborted.

Goal	Error handling::download files
Pre-condition	Session has been successfully rendered on Renderfarm.fi
Test suite/case description/steps	The workflow part downloads the results, but cannot comply.
Expected result	The user is notified of the download error.

Goal	Error handling::status query
Pre-condition	A session has been created with Renderfarm.fi
Test suite/case description/steps	The user (workflow) queries Renderfarm.fi for status
Expected result	A status message is being returned. One of: in queue, rendering, done, cancelled.

Test Suit: outbound work

Goal	Authentication to partner
Pre-condition	Not authenticated with the targetted partner platform.
Test suite/case description/steps	Send the certificate to log in.
Expected result	The Renderfarm.fi backend has been authenticated to the targetted partner platform.

Goal	Send job
Pre-condition	A job containing a simulation and successfull authentication with the targetted partner platform.
Test suite/case description/steps	Schedule the job and transmit the necessary data files
Expected result	The job has been scheduled for processing

Goal	Fluid baking
Pre-condition	A job with fluid simulation has been added.
Test suite/case description/steps	Calculate the fluid simulation for the given job.
Expected result	The fluid simulation has been baked.

Goal	Smoke baking
Pre-condition	A job with smoke simulation has been added.
Test suite/case description/steps	Calculate the smoke simulation for the given job.
Expected result	The smoke simulation has been baked.

Goal	Receive work
Pre-condition	A job has been completed on a partner grid.

Test suite/case description/steps	Download baked results from the partner.
Expected result	The baked results have been successfully received. A simulation baking generates a number of files per frame. Each of these results are available for retrieval

Goal	Integrate in original
Pre-condition	Result files have been retrieved from partner portal
Test suite/case description/steps	Reintegrate the baked results into Renderfarm.fi work units
Expected result	Work units with the baked simulation results have been created

Goal	Status query
Pre-condition	A job is scheduled or in progress at the targetted partner platform.
Test suite/case description/steps	Query the status. (workflow or remote gUse API)
Expected result	<p>A status message is returned. Possible status message envisaged at this point: UPLOADING The session data is being sent to the target grid WAITING The job is in queue and waiting to be processed on the target grid IN_PROGRESS The job is being processed on the target grid DOWNLOADING The results are being downloaded from the target grid ERROR An error has occured (any of upload, processing and downloading) CANCELLED A job has been cancelled on the target grid</p>

Goal	Error handling
Pre-condition	A job is being created or is in progress
Test suite/case description/steps	Handle errors that can occur during job handling on the targetted partner platform
Expected result	<p>The error is handled. Through status queries we find out what kind of errors have occured. Typical errors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • out of memory Both fluid and smoke simulation baking are expensive on memory usage. With high domain specific settings huge amounts are required • out of disk space Both fluid and smoke simulation generate large result files per frame. With high domain specific settings huge files will be created. • computational error Bugs in the simulation code may result in crashing blender instances. Log files and crash detection should give the necessary information to the workflow handler.

14 JRA2.8: Citizen web community gateway (EG)

Portal Name: Citizen Web Community Gateway

Organisation, Workpackage: EG (E-GROUP), WP8 – JRA2.8

Background for testing

The functions-to-be-tested are the GRID/CLOUD-related parts of the whole workflow. These parts have to communicate with server sides that are hosted by the GRID/CLOUD environment.

The affected steps (**Step 3, Step 4, Step 5**) of the whole process are described below:

Step 3 Professional OCR/ICR module

- The content of the scanned documents have to be recognized in order to make it processable for further steps.
- **This step needs OCR** (Optical Character Recognition), **ICR** (Intelligent Character Recognition) or perhaps **FR** (Form Recognition) solutions for analyzing typewritten or handwritten characters (or maybe voice recognition solution in case of audio files). The rate of recognized words, expressions can be better by using language-specific dictionaries but this semantic analysis rises the computation time of this step. This is an identified point where **GRID or CLOUD** is a possible solution for accelerating the process!

Step 4 Indexing and Metadata Processing module

- The metadata of the scanned documents must be given in order to enhance the functionality of searching and retrieving data.
- **This step needs human resource** to check automatically filled metadata in case automatic processing is supported. Otherwise the whole metadata structure shall be filled in by the human resource administrator which needs the most time in the whole process! If the recognized content of a document is available, an intelligent application (e.g. by using form recognition or keyword analysis) can decide automatically most of these parameters such as type of document (e.g. invoice) or issue date (e.g. 2011-10-01), but this analysis rises the computation time of this step. This is an identified point where **GRID or CLOUD** is a possible solution for accelerating the process!

Step 5 Cryptographic Service Provider module

- The scanned document and its metadata structure have to be packed together and signed.
- **This step needs some kind of cryptographic module such as OpenSSL or the product of E-GROUP, called SDX (Signed Document eXpert)** which is fully conform to international legal and technical regulations and creates XML electronic signatures. The created signatures have to be verified (after revocation period) in order to embed CRLs (Certificate Revocation Lists) or OCSP responses. If the electronic signature is valid, the related paper-based document can be destroyed, shredded.

SCI-BUS – Low-level design of Electronic Document Handling Gateway

Figure 1: The logical design of the whole architecture

Test Suites

Test Suites Module: OCR #1

Goal	The functionality of OCR module is tested.
Pre-condition	The content of the scanned document is split, and stored as PDF or TIFF file format (TIFF is the default setting).
Test suite/case description	Send the to-be-processed file to GRID/CLOUD.
Expected result	The function returns the recognized content as HTML or DOCX file format (HTML is the default setting).
Constraints for test execution	various file size and timeout values (based on POST settings) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected in case of failures unsupported file formats on input interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected unsupported file formats on output interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected

Test Suites Module: OCR #2

Goal	The functionality of OCR module is tested.
Pre-condition	The recognized content of the document is stored as separate HTML or DOCX files for each page (HTML is the default setting).
Test suite/case description	Send the to-be-processed file to GRID/CLOUD.
Expected result	The function returns the merged recognized content as HTML or DOCX file format (HTML is the default setting).
Constraints for test execution	various file size and timeout values (based on POST settings) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected in case of failures unsupported file formats on input interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected unsupported file formats on output interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected

Test Suites Module: Parser #1

Goal	The functionality of HTML or DOCX parser and inverted index creator module is tested.
Pre-condition	The content of the scanned document is recognized, and stored as HTML or DOCX file format (HTML is the default setting).
Test suite/case description	Send the to-be-processed file to GRID/CLOUD.
Expected result	The function returns the list of “expression-counter” pairs, where “expression” values are the words of content and “counter” values are the number of occurrences.
Constraints for test execution	various file size and timeout values (based on POST settings) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected in case of failures unsupported file formats on input interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected

Test Suites Module: Parser #2

Goal	The functionality of HTML or DOCX parser and inverted index creator module is tested.
Pre-condition	The content of the scanned document is recognized, and stored as HTML or DOCX file format (HTML is the default setting).
Test suite/case description	Send the to-be-processed file to GRID/CLOUD.
Expected result	The function returns the list of “expression-node” pairs, where “expression” values are the sections of content in a given layout container and “node” values are the XPath strings where content is stored.
Constraints for test execution	various file size and timeout values (based on POST settings) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected in case of failures unsupported file formats on input interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected

Test Suites Module: Parser #3

Goal	The functionality of HTML or DOCX parser and inverted index creator module is tested.
Pre-condition	The lists of “expression-value” and “expression-node” pairs are stored.
Test suite/case description	Send the to-be-processed file to GRID/CLOUD.
Expected result	The function returns the list of “expression-nodelist” pairs, where “expression” values are the words of content and “nodelist” values are the XPath strings where content is stored.

Test Suites Module: Parser #4

Goal	The functionality of HTML or DOCX parser and inverted index creator module is tested.
Pre-condition	The lists of “expression-nodelist” pairs are stored and pre-defined dictionary files and regular expression rules are available for loading.
Test suite/case description	Send the to-be-processed file to GRID/CLOUD.
Expected result	The function returns MIREG metadata structure of the input content as XML file format (XML is the default setting).
Constraints for test execution	various file size and timeout values (based on POST settings) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected in case of failures unsupported file formats on output interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • error messages are expected

15 JRA2.9: Astrophysics community science gateway (INAF)

Portal URL : VisIVOPortal.oact.inaf.it

Project Name: VisIVOGateway

Organisation, Workpackage: INAF, JRA2.9

Background for testing:

The test plan for INAF covers the tests that are required to ensure that the end users of the portal will successfully access all the VisIVO backend functionalities. The bulk of the processes will be handled through workflow patterns.

The areas to be tested can be roughly divided in areas for importing, filtering and viewing the data comprising the tests for result creation, result delivery, status checking and error handling.

For VisIVOGateway the following test activities have been identified:

- Testing of the Importer functionalities.
- Testing of the Filter functionalities.
- Testing of the Viewer functionalities.

This section gives an overview on the tests of the Importer which is almost completed now and of the Viewer which is under development.

The Importer Portlet uploads and converts user-supplied datasets into a VisIVO Binary Table (VBT).

VBTs are used by the Filter portlet for data processing and the Viewer portlet for display.

This document will be kept up-to-date during the project.

Pay specific attention to naming as they can change during the project phase.

Also changes in workflow and dataflow will be reflected here where needed.

At this point of the project the test cases represent a rough overview of the issues that need to be tested to ensure both proper working of the VisIVOGateway backend and the portal usability by the end users.

Test suites

Test Suite Name 1: Test of the Local Importer portlet

Goal	The purpose of this test is to validate the Local Importer portlet on testable input files and input parameters
Pre-condition	The user has a valid input file to be imported in the portal
Test suite/case description	The portal uploads the file and generates the output file (a VBT) using a workflow Given a registered user having an importable input file on its local machine, And relative appropriate parameters for the input file When the user selects the input file And set the appropriate parameters Then the user is ready to submit the job When the status is finished Then the user receives back the VBT available through the data management facility
Expected result	The VBT is available in the Internal Data Management facility and the user can download it and get information on the relative meta data (e.g. VBT storage path, VBT fields)

Test Suite Name 2: Test of the Viewer portlet

Goal	The purpose of this test is to validate the Viewer portlet on testable imported VBT
Pre-condition	The user has at least one VBT available in the Data Management facility
Test suite/case description	The portal generates an image from the user selected VBT locally using a VisIVOViewer Given a registered user having a VBT on the Data Management facility, And relative appropriate parameters for the visualization of the VBT When the user selects the VBT And set the appropriate parameters Then the user is ready to submit the view job When the image has been created Then the user receives back the image available through the data management facility
Expected result	The Image is available in the Internal Data Management facility and the user can download it

16 JRA2.10: Build and test public gateway for application developers (4D)

Portal: Build Portal - JRA2.10

Organisation: 4D Soft

Background for testing

The most important new implementation of the 4D Etics portal in the SCI-BUS project is the integration of the current submission service with the DCI Bridge. The current submission mechanism is governed by a service which transfers the jobs on the most suitable node in the pool. These nodes are static by means that they are up and running when the system operates. In contrast, a dynamic build server is identified by the DCI Bridge runtime. The required server will be started by DCI Bridge and when the build job finished the server will be shut down.

During testing we focus on the new implementations on testing the interface with DCI Bridge. Especially,

- Connections to DCI bridge for dynamically manage the available build servers
- Dynamic creation and proper configuration of servers
- The new DCI bridge accounting and billing portlet in 4DETICS
- Proper executions of 4D Etics jobs on the dynamic build servers

As for testing connections to DCI bridge, JRA1 people will provide information on using DCI Bridge client. Then test connections will be established to their test infrastructure.

Then dynamic build serves will be added in 4D Etics build server pool. Their lifecycle will be managed dynamically. For instance, if a required build server does not exist we can call for one from the DCI cloud. But firstly, we have to initialize all the build servers what we can use later on by installing the proper communication software on them (in our case condor).

Regarding new DCI Bridge accounting and billing portlet: as the DCI cloud connection services are not free of charge, we have to write our own portlet for that purpose to inform our users about the costs. Unfortunately, it is no possible to provide exact prices as it cannot be predicted how long their build will run.

As for proper job execution on the dynamic build servers, we have to verify all the type of DCI build servers such as the 4D Etics client is able to run on them, all the dependent software are installed properly on them and so on. The best approach is to run an 4D Etics job on them to test the correctness of the build servers.

All these new functionalities will be tested mostly at service and API level. However, a few business level end-to-end acceptance tests are also foreseen.

The main purpose of the scenario below is to verify the required functionalities of the Build Portal from end user point of view. To do so, business level acceptance tests to verify remote

job submission on the cloud and also to verify the payment service are to be implemented. The test steps, description is done in BDD (Behaviour Driven Development) style. More info on BDD can be found in the previous deliverable found in svn/SA2/Deliverables.

Test Suites

Test Suite Name1: Business scenario for selecting a Submitter and the appropriate job will be occurring in the 4D ETICS execution list and the correct submitter is selected

Goal	Validate that the correct submitter engine is selected
Pre-condition	Up and running Build Portal services and the user of the Build Portal is already registered. The project configuration (in our case for gUSE) under test is already created.
Test suite/case description, steps	<p>Feature: submitter selection</p> <p>User Story: Selecting CloudBroker submitter engine on the Build Portal and submit a build on gUSE project</p> <p>Scenario happy path</p> <p>Given a registered user "Smiths" And user have release manager rights on gUSE project. When user "Smiths" selects the latest gUSE release configuration, And selects "Remote Build" for the given configuration And selects "CloudBroker" submitter engine And clicks on "Submit" Button Then new job occurs in the Submission Page And the job has "pending" state And the job has "CloudBroker" submitter set</p> <p>Scenario insufficient privileges</p> <p>Given a registered user "Smiths" And user has not got release manager rights on gUSE project. When user "Smiths" selects the latest gUSE release configuration, Then user cannot click on "Remote Build" for the given configuration</p>
Expected result	The new job can be found in the execution pool with the appropriate settings

Test Suite Name2: Business scenario for creating a temporary build server through the DCI Bridge and CloudBroker services automatically

Goal	Validate that the missing platform will occur in the local condor pool and the build server initialization is working correctly!
Pre-condition	Up and running Build Portal services. Assuming that DCI Bridge client is initialized.
Test suite/case description, steps	<p>Feature: Temporary build server creation</p> <p>User Story: Automatic build server creation with the necessary initializations</p> <p>Scenario happy path</p> <p>Given a job with CloudBroker submitter set in the execution pool And job has "platformName" set to be executed on And "platformName" is in the supported platforms When waiting for "x" sec.</p>

	<p>Then on NMI portal view the new “platformName” must be occur! And the new platform is in “Unclaimed” state</p> <p>Scenario unsupported platform</p> <p>Given a job with CloudBroker submitter set in the execution pool And job has “platformName” set to be executed on And “platformName” is not supported When waiting for “x” sec. Then on NMI portal view the new “platformName” will not occur!</p>
Expected result	On NMI portal view the new “platformName” must be occur and will be ready to use by the original submission engine

Test Suite Name3: Business scenario for remote job execution on a temporary build server

Goal	To have end-to-end acceptance tests to validate the correctness of the remote job execution even on an temporary build server
Pre-condition	Build Portal services are up and running. The temporary build server with the appropriate platform (cannot be found in the local NMI pool) must be in the global NMI pool!
Test suite/case description, steps	<p>Feature: job execution on a temporary build server</p> <p>User Story: Create gUSE deployment packages using CloudBroker services</p> <p>Scenario happy path</p> <p>Given a job with CloudBroker submitter set in the execution pool And job has “platformName” set to be executed on And job has pending or running status And job has a user set with the appropriate email And “platformName” is in the global NMI pool When waiting for “x” sec. Then job has finished status And job packages and reports are available on portal And user receives an email about the job execution</p> <p>Scenario invalid temporary build server initialization</p> <p>Given a job with CloudBroker submitter set in the execution pool And job has “platformName” set to be executed on And job has pending or running status And “platformName” is in the global NMI pool When waiting for “x” sec. Then job has failed running or pending status</p>
Expected result	The user receives an email containing a link from where he could download the required packages. Also he receives a bill for using cloud services.

17 JRA2.11: Helio-physics gateway (TCD)

Portal Name: HELIOGate

Organisation, Workpackage: TCD, JRA 2.11

Background for testing:

The functionalities of the HELIOGate portal are not entirely defined as HELIO, a fellow project, is still under development and the HELIOGate portal will only cover functionalities that are either not developed within HELIO at the end of its duration or have a particular relevance for what regards visualization and workflows.

To better understand the test plan, it is important to understand that there are two level of tests.

- 1) Automated tests that cover those functionalities that can be covered with an automated system such as JUnit
- 2) User tests that need the intervention of a scientist for data validation. These are particularly relevant when it comes to the assessment of feature extraction and other codes that extract metadata from raw data.

This document will only cover the tests of point (1).

Each of the applications being tested consists in programs (written in IDL) executed in an IDL environment that exists on the fast and grid computation facilities at TCD.

The different test suites will cover all the layers encompassed by the application as it is described in Figure 1.

- JOB TESTS : Suite that consists in simple jobs to check the computational infrastructures, both fast and grid-based
- APPLICATION TESTS : Suites that test the single applications
- IDL TESTS : Suite that tests the IDL environment
- SUBMISSION TESTS : Suite that tests the execution of the abovementioned suites through the Job Submission System

Figure 1, Overview of the test suite

Test suites

Test Suite Name 1: Test of the IDL environment

Goal	The purpose of this test is to validate the IDL environment
Environment Prerequisites	IDL
Pre-condition	None
Test suite/case description	A set of simple IDL procedures (file download, test routines) are executed
Expected result	The expected results are returned by the IDL routines

Test Suite Name 2: Tests for each of the IDL applications

Goal	The purpose of this test is to validate each of the IDL applications
Environment Prerequisites	IDL, IDL applications
Pre-condition	None
Test suite/case description	Each IDL application has a test attached that will execute a significant subset of its execution space
Expected result	The expected results are returned by the each of the IDL application tests

Test Suite Name 3: Simple Job test

Goal	The purpose of this test is to validate the execution environment
Environment Prerequisites	Execution environment (grid and fast)
Pre-condition	None
Test suite/case description	A simple job to be executed on the fast and grid environment
Expected result	The output of the simple job

Test Suite Name 4: Submission Test

Goal	The purpose of this test is to validate the submission system
Environment Prerequisites	Job Submission System, IDL environment, IDL applications, Simple Job Test
Pre-condition	None
Test suite/case description	The submission, execution and output retrieval of all the test applications
Expected result	The output of other test suites

18 Conclusions coming from the collected test specifications

Portals to be implemented in SCI-BUS intend to serve a large number of user communities, therefore high quality software packages should be released. To achieve this goal, a certain number of working procedures are applied during the project lifecycle.

Firstly, regarding the implementation of the portals, in the time between major releases (one in the end of the first year and one in the end of the second year) frequent internal releases are recommended to be available for testing. Some kind of agility is intended to be introduced in the development lifecycle: frequent implementation, integration and testing phases will iterate, but this is of course up to the individual partners to decide.

Regarding the testing workload, basic unit tests are implemented by individual developers. High level system tests are to be implemented by the SA2 following the test specifications provided by each portal development team (JRA1 and JRA2). See the sections above.

This document contains a condensed information of the collected test cases focusing on the test descriptions. The original specifications from all the JRA1 and JRA2 partners are stored in the official project repository in svn (<https://cvs.lpds.sztaki.hu/scibus/wsvn/scibus/sa2/TestSpecifications/>). These specifications are live documents and will be updated as the project evolves.

- SA2 assisted this activity by providing test templates and by proposing test types that might be applied by eScience communities using gUSE/WS-Pgrade portal family. This initial test type recommendation can be found in the previous deliverable DSA51 (https://cvs.lpds.sztaki.hu/scibus/wsvn/scibus/sa2/Deliverables/DSA21/D51Integration_and_testing_strategy.doc). Also a testing tutorial was hold during the SCI-BUS project's kick-off meeting (see for more information https://cvs.lpds.sztaki.hu/scibus/wsvn/scibus/project_meetings/2011.10.18-21 - Kick-Off/SCI-BUS_ETICS_tutorial_October2011.pptx and https://cvs.lpds.sztaki.hu/scibus/wsvn/scibus/project_meetings/2011.10.18-21 - Kick-Off/SCI-BUS Kick-off Testing_October2011.pptx).

Here is the list of initially proposed test types in the order of importance:

- Deployment tests (eventually ETICS multinode mechanism see chapter 6.1 in DSA51)
- API tests (ASM api, i.e. cloud accessibility, connection)
- Service, Stress and Load tests (soapUI, Grinder, JMeter)
- Web tests, Browser compatibility tests (Selenium)
- Acceptance Tests (Robot Framework/Sikuli and or Selenium and other test libraries) and/or alternatively
- Acceptance test scenarios from user stories

- GUI functional tests

A detailed description of these test types and also a set of associated tools can be found in DSA51 section (see section 6 in

https://cvs.lpds.sztaki.hu/scibus/wsvn/scibus/sa2/Deliverables/DSA21/D51Integration_and_testing_strategy.doc).

When preparing test specifications, JRA2 portal developers concentrated especially on newly implemented features based on gUSE services. In addition to gUSE features, all JRA2 community members defined their individual requests. All these individual aspects are taken into account by SA2.

As a result, the initially proposed test types list might be refined following the results coming out from the JRA1 and JRA2 tests specifications. Particularly, from the collected information and from the on-going JRA1 related testing work might be concluded that applying the following test types makes the most sense for SCI-BUS community:

- Deployment tests of the gUSE/WS-PGrade portal and the JRA2 portals using gUSE/WS-PGrade
- API and service tests for testing of WFI (workflow interpreter service of the gUSE) and DCI-Bridge related services
- End-to-end acceptance tests (web functional tests and browser compatibility tests)

The correctness of the deployments can be verified by running self-test workflows as service tests. One general approach of such a method is described in more detail in section 4. This approach is already implemented for gUSE/WS-Pgrade portal deployment's verification. It can be run through the 4D Etics portal - the project level build and test environment of the SCI-BUS project. An other approach for testing the workflows is presented by JRA22 portal (for more information see 8). Their approach now can be used just for their portal. Later on, it will be verified it's applicability for other portals respectively.

Additionally to deployment tests augmented with self-test workflows, service tests of the DCI-Bridge and also the CloudBroker plugin integration seems to be a general interest of the majority of communities. Likewise, end-to-end web acceptance tests and browser compatibility tests are also required by project partners.

As a conclusion, any above mentioned test type may be used if deemed appropriate for the particular community. As the project evolves, new assumptions may also be added that are reasoned to be suitable to the project. Awareness of such requirements can help SA2 keep ahead of the requirements and to prepare the test development and running environment accordingly.

19 Summary

This document presented the test specifications based on main use cases of the SCI-BUS project. Dues to the nature of the project, JRA1 related tests specifications are described in more detail. JRA2 portals' specifications are mostly high-level summaries.

The test specification document is a living document. Its content will be updated as the project evolves and new implementations will be available for testing.

20 Appendix: Template for test specification

Portal Name:

Organisation, Workpackage:

Background for testing

(Give as much information as you can on the required testing activity)

General Assumptions related to testing

(Fill just one template for your portal)

Test Adequacy Criteria	<i>Describes the criteria when to stop testing. Which is the condition when SA2 could consider the portal ready for release? The most obvious case is when all the specified tests run without error.</i>
Schedule	<i>Specifies the project month when the testing could be started.</i>
Contact Person	<i>Email or skype address of the person to be contacted, who is involved in work with SA2</i>
General testing related notes, issues to be decided	<i>Lists here all the questions and issues, existing blocking conditions which have to be further discussed to reach some kind of agreement at latest in Antalya meeting.</i>

Test Suite Template(s)

(Fill as many templates as you consider important for your activity)

Goal	<i>Describes the high level purpose of the test case. Mentions the functionalities, services to be verified.</i>
Environment Prerequisites	<i>Lists all the required environmental needs that are necessary for running the tests. In case of the SCI-BUS project, the default environment is 4D ETICS Build Portal.</i>
Pre-condition	<i>Gives the prerequisites for this test to be executed.</i>
Test suite/case description	<i>Describes the steps is to be executed and the input data.</i>

Expected result	<i>Gives the desired result of the test.</i>
Test type to implement	<i>Recommends the test type (service, API, web, functional, performance, other) to be implemented for this test case.</i>
Constraints for test execution	<i>Specifies if there are special constraints for this test to be executed. For example, security issues, certificates, legacy code, proprietary code, other issues.</i>
Priority	<i>Gives the priority of the test (importance for the project).</i>
Working Procedure	<i>Describes the most appropriate collaboration approach between SA2 and individual portal developers in order to implement and conduct the tests and later on to maintain them.</i>
Issues	<i>Lists all the questions, issues that should be discussed further in order to conduct the test case.</i>